

SUPERSATURATION LIMITS OF NON-AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS.

PART I

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Limits of supersaturation in non-aqueous solutions of non-electrolytes have been studied. The value of $(T_s - T)\lambda$ has been calculated. From the value of $(T_s - T)\lambda$ the value of the radius of the stable crystal nucleus has been calculated. The value of 'r' has got the same order in different systems *i.e.*, the order is 10^{-6} cm.

The effect of heating on the limits of supersaturation of non-aqueous solutions of non-electrolytes has been studied. The effect of heating is observed in most of the systems. The product of concentration (c) and the fluidity ' ϕ ' has been calculated. It is found for the systems having ' $c\phi$ ' value more than 30, heating effect is negligible. Certain exceptions to the ' $c\phi$ ' rule are noticed. These are accounted for by the low mutual affinity among the molecules of the solutes.

In a number of papers published by Ram Gopal from this laboratory (this *Journal*, 1943, *et seq.*), it has been shown that $(T_s - T)$ is fairly constant in aqueous solutions of some electrolytes. In other cases $(T_s - T)$ has, however, been found to increase with successive heating and cooling. It has also been observed that there is a third type of aqueous solution which does not crystallise even after sufficient cooling. Further, it has been observed that in general $(T_s - T)$ increases with heating in the case of a number of aqueous solutions. In this paper an attempt has been made to find out if these generalisations are also applicable to solutions of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents.

We have here classified our data into three different types. Table I shows those with very little or no heating effect. Table II shows those with heating effect, *i.e.* in these systems $(T_s - T)$ increases with successive heating and cooling. In order to find out the value of $(T_s - T)$ the first temperature of spontaneous crystallisation has been taken as other values of $(T_s - T)$ are increased due to heating effect. In Table III there are, however, certain types that do not spontaneously crystallise even on considerable cooling.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The experimental method followed is the same as that of Ram Gopal (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 187). Results obtained are given below in Tables I, II and III.

TABLE I

Solute.	Solvent.	Temperature range studied.	$(T_s - T)$ (average).	Remarks.
1. Naphthalene	Carbon tetrachloride	25°, 30°, 35°, 40°, 45°, 50°	2.9	No heating effect after heating for 11 hours.
2. <i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	Bromobenzene	50°, 55°, 60°, 65°, 70°, 75°	10.5	„
3. <i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	Propyl alcohol	50°, 55°, 60°, 65°, 70°	10.2	„
4. Anthracene	Benzene	45°, 50°, 55°, 60°, 65°, 70°	7.9	„
5. Naphthalene	Aniline	30°, 35°, 40°, 45°, 50°, 55°	9.2	„

TABLE II

Solute.	Solvent.	Temperature range studied.	$(T_s - T)$ (average)	Remarks.
1. Naphthalene	Benzene	30°, 35°, 40°, 45°, 50°, 55°	5.6	Heating effect after heating for 3 hours but after that T does not change even after heating for 11 hours.
2. Naphthalene	Chlorobenzene	35°, 40°, 45°, 50°, 55°, 60°	4.3	"
3. "	Nitrobenzene	30°, 40°, 45°, 50°, 55°, 60°	7.9	"
4. "	Toluene	35°, 40°, 45°, 50°, 55°, 60°	5.5	"
5. "	Methyl alcohol	25°, 30°, 35°, 40°, 45°	4.3	"
6. "	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	35°, 40°, 45°, 50°, 55°, 60°	13.5	"
7. "	Acetic acid	30°, 35°, 40°, 45°, 50°, 55°	7.4	"
8. Acenaphthene	Chloroform	35°, 40°, 45°, 48°, 50°, 52°	16.6	"
9. Diphenyl	Benzene	35°, 40°, 45°, 50°, 55°	15.6	Heating effect
10. Acenaphthene	<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	40°, 45°, 50°, 55°, 60°	18.0	"
11. Benzoic acid	Benzene	50°, 55°, 60°, 65°, 78°, 83°	8.0	"
12. Salicylic acid	Benzene	45°, 50°, 55°, 60°, 65°, 70°	10.0	"
13. <i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	Benzene	40°, 45°, 50°, 55°, 60°, 65°	16.8	"
14. <i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	Benzene	55°, 60°, 65°, 70°, 75°, 80°	22.2	"
15. Acenaphthene	Toluene	45°, 50°, 55°, 60°, 65°, 70°	25.0	"
16. Benzoic acid	Toluene	55°, 60°, 65°, 70°, 75°, 80°	19.1	"
17. "	Acetone	45°, 50°, 55°, 57°, 60°	12.5	"
18. Acenaphthene	Methyl alcohol	30°, 35°, 40°, 45°, 50°	10.1	"
19. <i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	Bromobenzene	45°, 50°, 55°, 60°, 65°, 70°	11.5	"
20. Acetanilide	Chloroform	45°, 50°, 52°, 55°	23.2	"

TABLE III

Methyl alcohol—Acetanilide, Methyl alcohol—Diphenylamine, Hexane—Diphenylamine,
Acetone—resorcinol.

From the above results it has been tested whether the expression, which has been deduced from the equation of Jones and Partington (*Phil. Mag.*, 1915, 29, 35), remains constant in these systems also.

Results for the expression $(T_s - T)$ are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Solvent.	Solution Solute.	λ in kilo Joules.	$(T_s - T)$. (°C)	$(T_s - T)$ (in calories).
1. Benzene	Naphthalene	18.5	5.6°	24670
2. "	Benzoic acid	14.2	8.0	27050
3. Toluene	Naphthalene	17.8	5.5	23450
4. Methyl alcohol	"	17.7	4.3	18130
5. Acetone	Benzoic acid	12.1	12.5	36020
6. Acetic acid	Naphthalene	17.5	7.4	30740
7. Aniline	"	19.8	9.2	43400
8. Benzene	Salicylic acid	23.9	10.0	56910
9. "	Diphenyl	18.0	15.6	66860
10. Toluene	Benzoic acid	14.2	19.1	64600
11. Chloroform	Acenaphthene	18.8	16.6	74310
12. Methyl alcohol	"	25.9	10.1	62030
13. Chloroform	Acetanilide	18.4	23.2	101800
14. Toluene	Acenaphthene	20.0	25.0	119100
15. Propyl alcohol	"	28.5	18.0	122100
16. Benzene	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	15.9	22.2	84360

The values of λ have been taken from the International Critical Table, 1928, Vol. V, pp. 151-154).

From the results given above it appears that the value of $(T_s - T)$ is not constant but varies from 18130 to 122100.

The relation between $(T_s - T)$ and σV_m

In the derivation of the equation

$$\lambda(T_s - T) = 2\sigma V_m \times T_s / r \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

it was assumed that if T_s remains constant in the case of similar systems then $(T_s - T)$ must vary directly as σV_m . If σ and V_m are known for a particular system, then $\frac{(T_s - T)\lambda}{\sigma V}$

can be calculated from equation (1). The values so calculated are given Table V.

TABLE V

System.	$\frac{(T_s - T)\lambda}{\sigma V_m}$	$r \times 10^{-6}$ cm.	System.	$\frac{(T_s - T)\lambda}{\sigma V_m}$	$r \times 10^{-6}$ cm.
Benzene—Naphthalene	5.51	2.7	Aniline—Naphthalene	9.69	1.5
Toluene	5.23	2.9	Benzene— <i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	12.5	1.2
MeOH	5.09	3.7	Do—Diphenyl	11.3	1.3
CH ₃ COOH	6.86	2.2	CHCl ₃ —Acetanilide	23.4	0.63

From the results in Table V, it is rather interesting to note that when the solute is the same and the solvent is different, the value $(T_s - T) \lambda / \sigma V_m$ appears to be constant.

From the results given in Table V, the value of r has also been calculated from the equation (1), and these values have been calculated for each separate system. (For value of r see column 3 of Table V). It is very interesting to note that the order of the radius of the stable crystal nucleus is the same as has been determined by other workers.

Effect of Heating on the Limits of Supersaturation

From the results cited in Tables I and II it appears that effect of heating is a general phenomenon as has been observed by other workers. Only a few systems show a small or negligible heating effect.

TABLE VI

	Systems	T_s	S_w	$(T_s - T)$	ηT	$c = S_w/M$	$c\phi$
1	CCl ₄ Naphthalene	40°	56.4	3.0	0.01160	0.4375	37.72
2	CHCl ₃ Acenaphthene	35	39.0	15.5	0.01040	0.2593	24.36
3	Aliline Naphthalene	40	60.0	9.0	0.02461	0.4690	19.05
4	C ₆ H ₅ Br <i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	40	61.3	9.0	0.02060	0.2610	12.66
5	Benzene Naphthalene	40	118.0	6.0	0.00940	0.9220	98.10
6	C ₆ H ₅ Cl „	40	90.0	4.5	0.01045	0.7000	68.70
7	Toluene „	40	100.0	5.0	0.008459	0.7810	92.32
8	Hexane „	40	41.1	7.5	0.004255	0.3210	75.47
9	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol „	40	23.0	14.5	0.01880	0.1797	9.56
10	Acetic acid „	40	28.0	8.5	0.01140	0.2188	19.20
11	Toluene Acenaphthene	40	47.0	22.0	0.00953	0.3052	30.00
12	CH ₃ OH „	40	6.0	9.0	0.00506	0.0039	7.70
13	Benzene <i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	40	163.0	18.0	0.01130	0.6910	61.00
14	„ Benzoic acid	40	22.00	8.0	0.00710	0.1803	25.40
15	C ₆ H ₅ NO ₂ Naphthalene	40	75.0	7.8	0.01670	0.5860	35.10
16	CH ₃ OH „	35	11.6	4.0	0.005901	0.09060	15.36

Viscosity ηT corresponding to the temperature of first spontaneous crystallisation i.e., T has been given.

According to Hinshelwood and Hartley (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 43, 78) the heating effect is due to decrease in the catalytic activity of the colloidal dust particles. The concentration of the dust particles present in the beginning will be gradually lowered during the process of heating and shaking. As the concentration of the solute remains constant in a particular experiment, the decrease in the number of dust particles will diminish the number of successful molecular collisions, and thus the value of $(T_s - T)$ will go on increasing with successive heating and crystallisation or redissolution.

In a previous paper it has been shown that the value of ' c ' where c is the concentration expressed in g. mols. of solute per 100 g. of solvent and ' ϕ ' is the fluidity, to a large extent measures whether there will be any heating effect or not, as fluidity like concentration controls the molecular collisions. It may be expected that the value of ' $c\phi$ ' will control the capacity of forming active centres in a system which leads to crystallisation.

The results of ' $c\phi$ ' values are given in Table VI. The values of ' $c\phi$ ' are taken from the results obtained in this laboratory (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 39, 33) where it was not possible to determine viscosity, it has been interpolated from the results. The same temperature of saturation T_s has been considered in almost all the cases.

The results show that in cases where heating effect is very small or negligible the value of ' $c\phi$ ' is high. Generally in solutions in which ' $c\phi$ ' value is below 30, there is heating effect, but there are few exceptions. These exceptions remain to be explained. We have been regarding the molecules and ions as simple particles of matter, identical in all cases without any specific or individual characteristic of their own. This simple view, though highly helpful in explaining the qualitative properties of solutions, is not applicable to crystal formation from a supersaturated solution. It has been emphasised in previous papers that the attraction between the lattice forming units is necessary for the nucleus formation. If this attraction between the lattice forming units is low, it is possible that no crystalline centres may be formed even though ' $c\phi$ ' values indicate a large probability of molecular impacts. The low mutual affinity among the molecules of organic substances is shown by their easy subliming nature at low temperatures and their low melting points.

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